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The Electric Nature of our Climate and it's Change
*<References included in body of document intentionally
for better readability and easier verification>*

Introduction:

According to euronews at 2:40am on Feb 7th 2022 forty starlink satellites from Space X created a spectacular light show in the skies over Puerto Rico when they fell back to earth "right after having been launched".

It turns out they were launched during a "solar storm" (a time of peak solar winds) which heated earth's atmosphere enough that it expanded.

As Earth's atmosphere expanded further out into space it caused the small satellites to experience physical resistance/drag, The additional atmospheric resistance/drag decreased their speed (orbital velocity) enough that out of the forty nine satellites launched "all but nine were lost."

I believe this event provides the clearest evidence yet of the true driving force behind the climate on earth - and its change. Fully exploring the path energy from the Sun must follow as well as detailing the interactions of its use by earth's ecosystems might provide new insight into some antiquated ideals about the electrical nature of our planet that are at least a hundred years old, were never based on evidence, and are in dire need of updating.

Atmospheric Path Details:

As solar electrical energy approaches our planet it first encounters earth's hydrogen layer which extends out from its surface beyond its moon and begins its conversion from electrical energy to chemical energy by ionizing the hydrogen

Hydrogen exists as a highly combustible, diatomic gas with the molecular formula of H₂. When introduced into a low pressure plasma system [such as in our upper atmosphere], the hydrogen atoms [begin to] dissociate and ionize,

(<https://www.thierry-corp.com/plasma-knowledgebase/hydrogen-h2-plasma>)

The electrical energy then reaches earth's magnetic shield known as the Van Allen Radiation belt where due to the solar winds high voltage , and extreme temperature causes the hydrogen to emit high energy extreme ultraviolet light/radiation as it ionizes producing a UV Airglow .

“Solar extreme ultraviolet (EUV) radiation photoionizes the neutral constituents of the upper atmosphere, producing free electrons and ions”

(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/topics/earth-and-planetary-sciences/extreme-ultraviolet-radiation>)

“The Van Allen radiation belt is a zone of energetic charged particles, most of which originate from the solar wind. The particles are captured by and held around a planet by that planet’s magnetic field. It surrounds Earth, containing a nearly impenetrable barrier that prevents the fastest, most energetic electrons from reaching Earth”

(<https://spacecenter.org/what-are-the-van-allen-radiation-belts/>)

Recent observations revealed that the energy of electrons in the Van Allen radiation belts can go up to so-called ultra-relativistic energies. These electrons with temperatures above 100 Billion degrees Fahrenheit, move so fast that their energy of motion is much higher than their energy of rest given by Einstein's famous $E=mc^2$ formula.

(<https://scitechdaily.com/giant-particle-accelerator-in-the-sky-extremely-high-energy-electrons-within-the-van-allen-radiation-belts/>)

The Path of energy then Diverges based on its type

The solar wind's electrical energy from the Sun then follows this "path of least resistance" to the planet's surface due to the conductive nature of the ionized pathway already established by the earth magnetic field (Van Allen Belt). So the "solar electrical energy" now follows Earth's "magnetic fields electrical energy" into the south pole.

As the High energy extreme ultraviolet light/radiation continues toward the planets surface Hydrogen returns to its neutral state and it produces a red airglow

[ionized Hydrogen] releases a photon of wavelength 656.3 nm when it recaptures an electron and returns to its neutral state

(<https://astronomy.swin.edu.au/cosmos/i/ionised+hydrogen>)

The high-energy extreme ultraviolet light/radiation then reaches the oxygen layer causing the ionization of the oxygen producing a blue-green Airglow and highly reactive chemicals known as "Reactive Oxygen Species" like Ozone, hydrogen peroxide, etc.

Oxygen atoms play a crucial role in the production of auroral light. Above 100 km in altitude, the atmosphere primarily consists of oxygen atoms and nitrogen molecules. Solar extreme ultraviolet light dissociates molecular oxygen into atoms. The green light observed in aurorae comes from highly

energetic oxygen atoms that decay from a higher energy level to a lower, but still excited energy level.

(<https://atoptics.co.uk/blog/glowing-gases-aurorae/>)

“Oxidation reactions are ubiquitous and play key roles in the chemistry of the atmosphere, in water treatment processes, and in aerobic organisms. Ozone (O₃), hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂), hydrogen polyoxides (H₂O_x, x > 2), associated hydroxyl and hydroperoxyl radicals (HO_x = OH and HO₂), and superoxide and ozonide anions (O₂⁻ and O₃⁻, respectively) are the primary oxidants in these systems. They are commonly classified as reactive oxygen species (ROS).”

(<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/25688469/>)

The energy (plasma) produced by the ionized Oxygen then causes ignition where it interacts with neutral state hydrogen and oxygen. The resulting combustion produces heat, light in the form of a blue flame, and atmospheric water. This layer of combustion would be what divides the Thermosphere from the Mesosphere. <see *Graphic Below*>

<Image Courtesy of NASA web page called [Ionosphere Graphics](#)>

Any remaining electrical energy/radiation then continues to the surface and is absorbed by its life forms. (An example of this would be solar radiation and photosynthesis)

Surface Path Details

The electrical energy redirected to the south pole by earth's magnetic field becomes what's known as "telluric current" as it enters the planet and induces a magnetohydrodynamic effect as it travels across its surface from south to north.

magnetohydrodynamics is “the branch of physics that deals with the motion of electrically conductive fluids, especially plasmas, in magnetic fields.”

(<https://www.dictionary.com/browse/magnetohydrodynamics>)

Another way to describe the effect is through "lenz's law"

“the direction of the electric current induced in a conductor by a changing magnetic field is such that the magnetic field created by the induced current opposes changes in the initial magnetic field.”

(https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/Lenz%27s_law)

So with the direction of earth's magnetic field fixed, and its surface the electrical conductor, then the opposing magnetic field creates an electromotive force responsible for the planet's rotation.

Exceptions to surface conduction

areas over the planet's surface where the telluric current can not travel (due to greater resistance) would be reflected as gaps in earth's magnetic field /Van Allen belt in its upper atmosphere (but due to earth's rotation would be shifted slightly to the west of the surface area void of telluric current)

So any “gap/hole” in the magnetic field/Van Allen Belt would mean the Sun's electrical energy begins to encounter a higher resistance and begins to route away from that area in the

atmosphere resulting in Less Airglow, a substantial reduction in the volume of Atmospheric Reactive Oxygen Species created (for example less Ozone), and allows large amounts of high energy solar radiation/plasma to continue toward the surface

reduction of the ozone layer in the upper stratosphere over the South Atlantic region can modify the radiative flux at the top of the atmosphere and hence can cause changes in the weather and climate patterns, including cloud coverage.

[\(https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC6237378/\)](https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC6237378/)

If the area of poor electrical surface conduction and its corresponding magnetic field “gap” reach sufficient size the electrical component of the solar winds (plasma) , absent its normal path of least resistance, travels further down toward the planet's surface. It would then encounter the area where the oxygen and hydrogen mix causing direct ignition (instead of indirect - by way of ionization).

The increased combustion results in volume increases of heat, light and water production as well as large atmospheric low pressure systems. This higher rate of conversion of atmospheric O₂ and H₂ to water would also be the cause of what’s known as “Bomb Cyclones” and could easily add to ocean level rise.

(At its extreme it would convert earth's atmosphere to what's observed of mars atmosphere)

"A bomb cyclone occurs when atmospheric pressure at the center of the cyclone drops rapidly. In order to approximately qualify, the pressure needs to drop about 1 [millibar], or more, every hour over a 24-hour period," (Quote from John Moore, a public affairs specialist and meteorologist for the National Weather Service)

[<https://www.cbsnews.com/news/what-is-bomb-cyclone-winter-storm-weather-explained/>](https://www.cbsnews.com/news/what-is-bomb-cyclone-winter-storm-weather-explained/)

“Water exists on Mars but the atmosphere is too thin for it to last long on the surface in a liquid state. Instead, water on Mars is found below the surface of the polar regions as water-ice and also as seasonal briny water flows down hillsides and crater walls.”

(<https://www.space.com/16903-mars-atmosphere-climate-weather.html>)

The southern atlantic anomaly would be the result of a large portion of earth's surface losing its ability to conduct the telluric current.

the "southern Atlantic anomaly" in which A satellite/spacecraft at 440 km above earth's surface (around the altitude of the ISS) will experience a 1000 times increase in radiation exposure during the time it is passing through the South Atlantic Anomaly.

(<https://adsabs.harvard.edu/full/2005ICRC....2..353D>)

A 1000 times increase in solar radiation is a lot of extra energy in the form of heat and would have been the cause of the southern hemisphere of the planet heating at a faster rate than the northern hemisphere. (*note* there may be evidence this fact has changed, please see “related concepts” section below)

It's also having the effect of melting the Antarctic ice sheet which is then injecting fresh water into the oceans causing the catastrophic effect of lowering the salt content ratio of our oceans.

Pure water is a poor conductor of electricity. However, when salt is dissolved in water, the solution becomes an electrolyte that easily conducts electricity..

Saltwater has a greater conductance range than estuaries and rivers because of the high salt ion content (35 ppt; parts per thousand), therefore the conductivity of seawater is dependent on the salinity and also the temperature of the water.

(<https://atlas-scientific.com/blog/water-conductivity-range/>)

The additional freshwater from the melting Antarctic Ice sheet would affect the salinity

of the water over the entire Falkland plateau increasing its electrical resistance and lowering its ability to support the telluric current.

"showing cooling and freshening for the decade as a consequence of a higher Antarctic Intermediate Water (AAIW) contribution and of a decrease in the Sub-antarctic Mode Water (SAMW) stratum." as stated in the abstract titled "Differences between 1999 and 2010 across the Falkland Plateau: fronts and water masses"

https://digital.csic.es/bitstream/10261/154220/1/Perez_Hernandez_et_al_2017.pdf

According to Thermohaline circulation the circulation of water in the oceans begins in the Earth's polar regions. The force driving it is when ocean water at the poles gets very cold, sea ice forms. Salt does not freeze so the surrounding seawater gets saltier, increases in density, and sinks. (so "cold salty water sinks to the bottom of the oceans and warm fresh water rises to the surface"). Everything I've ever read concerning the slowing of this circulation attributes it to CO2 build up and "Climate Change" but never considers the change over time of the one component that is so important to the process that it's in the name; "haline" means "salinity". (salinity of the major oceans worldwide are dropping)

The ocean's salinity levels also directly dictate the amount of carbon dioxide the water can hold. The positive sodium ion in the oceans salt creates Alkaline surface waters, which drawdown carbon dioxide (CO2) from the atmosphere. The chemical changes that occur when CO2 is absorbed by seawater are called "ocean acidification".

The problem we are currently experiencing with the growing ocean acidification layer is in the "back end process" where the contents of that acidic layer are then supposed to convert to sodium bicarbonate.

That final conversion requires an electron donor catalyst normally supplied in the form of telluric current.

However, if the salinity of the ocean surface water is such that it doesn't provide the path of least resistance for the telluric current, then It will find a path around that area of increased resistance/lower conductance.

Leaving the sodium ion bound in the acid layer causes it to build up and prevents its availability to remove CO₂ from the atmosphere. (The current explanation for "Climate Change").

At this point it would be irresponsible of me to continue without bringing your attention to the realization that this discussion outlines that:

- earth's oceans have a completely independent method for CO₂ regulation
- As compared to earth's atmospheric CO₂ regulation”

“Earth's atmospheric CO₂ regulation is driven by the food chain relationship between plant and animal life on the planet” and the oceans ability to draw down atmospheric CO₂ is a balancing mechanism that allows us to breathe at ocean level.

“plants produce food for animals” and “animals produce food for plants” and the interference with the earth's atmospheric CO₂ regulation process (by having its populace reduce its carbon footprint to NET-0) will upset that balance in the food chain relationship resulting in catastrophic effects to earth's plant life which in turn will result in catastrophic effects to its animal life.

Furthermore, if the ultimate goal of climate activism is to reverse ocean acidification, then they need to realize that it CAN NOT be accomplished by reducing atmospheric CO2 levels. (Because the equilibrium (or balance) failure IS due to the failure of a very specific process critical to overall system stability. The lack of sufficient sodium ions will directly prevent the ocean's ability to regulate its homeostasis.)

It's the salt content and availability of telluric current that drives the balance.

Conclusion:

It was the currently weakend, disorganized, and patchy nature of earth's magnetic field during the launch of the starlink satellites that ultimately failed to properly regulate the sun's energy during the solar storm which allowed the extreme expansion of earth's atmosphere that caused the loss of the forty satellites.

Additionally the root cause of climate change is not CO2 rise (which is actually a symptom of the "lack of available sodium ions in the ocean waters"). But instead is the dropping Salt levels in the oceans.

Mitigation:

- raising the salt level in the ocean
 - There are two natural "evaporation ponds" mixed into the geology of our planet.
 - the Utah Salt Flats in the United States
 - the mountains around the Dead Sea in Israel.

(all of that salt in those locations originated in our oceans. Physically returning it to the Atlantic and Pacific oceans will normalize the climate and repair most of the damage to the oceans.)

- Re-establishes a path of least resistance over poor areas of conduction
- causing the conversion of acid to bicarbonate in those areas and also patches and strengthens magnetic shield
- The reduction of the oceans acid layer AND Restoration of magnetic shield uniformity/strength
 - prevents larger amounts of the sun's electrical energy from converting to heat or directly reaching earth's surface
 - and restores the oceans ability to properly regulate its CO2.
- lowering overall planet temperature and
- stabilizes the climate

Closing comments:

● *Building a perfect society is a lot like constructing the world's tallest high rise. For either to stand the test of time you can't compromise their integrity during construction. A Good construction company is an honest construction company and they understand that using substandard parts, operating with faulty equipment or failing to follow the blueprints inevitably results in someone getting hurt.*

(In an ideal society it would be entirely unacceptable to build its foundation using "that" as its cornerstone)

- *So if the construction blueprints of your utopia require that people be sacrificed as a catalyst for its creation, then you have already failed.*
- *It will only be when you accept that you currently have a construction crew of 8 billion people that your ideal society will have a chance to survive and flourish*
- *you must get them to work together like a family.*
- *They must understand and willingly agree to Do the job you want them to and*
- *They must respect and help each other while they work.*
- *Every crew member clocks in when they arrive and out when they leave and*
- *It's because all people have equal value that no one is left behind.*

- *I understand politically that the globalists are using climate change to try to secure influence over the nations of the world right now.*
- *however by the time they finished asserting control it will be too late. catastrophic changes to the climate will have occurred making parts of our world uninhabitable.*
- *additionally, the methods being used right now to assert control are immoral at best. To establish a Utopian society means that everyone must be in agreement. TO eliminate people because they won't agree means that you will never achieve your utopian vision. (because you've had to hand control to immoral people for its creation and they won't ever let go of that power.)*
- *The solution to establish a "one world government" is to handle this crisis the "right way".*
- *the people of the world will do as you ask because they trust you NOT by manipulating economic, health, education, and social systems to control them. (we all know what i'm referring to here)*
- *it will take years to accomplish*
- *you might have to start by using shipping vessels to deliver salt to some of the worst areas of the oceans to prevent climate issues from becoming worse.*
- *The solution will require all countries of the world to cooperate and coordinate bringing them together to mitigate the crisis for the future of all humanity.*
- *The one world government will establish its credibility by truly uniting the people of the world behind this one cause and gain their loyalty.*
- *you'll need to prevent corporations from having the ability to influence or corrupt politicians. By establishing rules that limit their "profit per employee". anything above a certain range they should be penalized and if not corrected forced into a "not for profit" status. (this will force them to lower the cost of their goods or pay their employees more and disincentivize conversion to automation)*
- *reject people, churches, government, organizations, and corporations looking to establish control or influence government decisions freeing you to "do the right thing".*
- *and stop subscribing to the concept that "the needs of the many outweigh the needs of a few"*

in a truly utopian society "the needs of everyone would be handled and no person would be left

behind"

Related Concepts:

1. the combustion layer

- a. is the reason why the daytime sky is blue. .
- b. is the reason our planet glows from outer space
- c. Is the reason why we can't see the stars during the daytime.
- d. Has a direct influence of high and low pressure areas in our atmosphere.
- e. Impacts the atmospheric rivers.

Theoretically Solar storms would drastically increase the rate of combustion under areas such as the southern Atlantic anomaly and would result in drastic fluctuations in the items listed in sections A through e above

Thereby directly influencing the kind of unusual climate events we are currently observing around the world.

2. Fluctuations in solar output result in fluctuations in the telluric current, which would also translate to fluctuations in electromotive force which means fluctuations in the planet's rotational speed.

The resulting torque could easily affect plate tectonics resulting in earthquakes.

3. You'll note that there is no mention of the earth producing the current needed to support its magnetic field (by way of "convection", etc). Furthermore, even if it could create an "electrical potential" in that manner it would simply short circuit by producing eddy currents inside *the same medium in which it was created*.

4. As the electrical energy from the sun crosses through Earth's atmosphere following the magnetic field into the south pole it causes the southern lights but the ionization path occurs downward toward the planet surface..

And where the electrical energy from the telluric current crosses through Earth's atmosphere following the magnetic field out of the North Pole it causes the northern lights but the ionization path occurs upward away from the planet's surface.

So because the northern lights path of ionization is moving away from us on the surface, we can see the ignition point in the sky. It is the bright line in the northern sky at the bottom of the Aurora Borealis. (The same "ignition line" also occurs for southern lights but you can only see it from outer space.)

So when you can see the northern lights as close to the equator as San Francisco or Mississippi (happening lately with alarming frequency) it means that the telluric current is struggling to find a path of least resistance all the way to the North Pole.

The result would be that earth's magnetic field HAS NOT protected the top quarter of the planet as it did before 1979 resulting in significant amounts of additional heat reaching its surface under that area.

“during the last 43 years the Arctic has been warming nearly four times faster than the globe, which is a higher ratio than generally reported in literature” from the abstract titled **“The Arctic has warmed nearly four times faster than the globe since 1979”**

(<https://www.nature.com/articles/s43247-022-00498-3>)

This would be the most rational explanation for the observed magma temperature increases in the volcanic calderas under both the Hawaiian islands and the Yellowstone National Park in the United States (causing the most recent Hawaiian volcanic eruptions all the way to the Yellowstone supervolcano re-activation..)

- proper consideration of this paragraph on a larger scale leads to discussion over the “drastic spike in volcanic activity WorldWide over the past ten years” AND how the “non-newtonian features of magnetohydrodynamic fluids involving the effect of eddy currents generated in them when surrounded magnetic fields” would be a greater driving factor to the volcanic uptick, than the increased heat of the magma itself. (***“Spoiler Alert”*** But that discussion would have to be the topic of an entirely different paper. The information discussed in this paper would be required to establish the needed background and

foundation)

NOTE An eruption of Yellowstone supervolcano would eject enough debris into the atmosphere that it would block all sunlight from reaching the Earth's surface for decades, ending all life on our planet.

I guess what I'm trying to say here is that we are reaching a point where no one can "really" deny the effects of climate change anymore. However, the systematic destruction of global economies and agriculture, the shutdown of the fossil fuel industry, implementing population reduction, shutting down dialogue by saying they "Own the Science", and strapping "fart bags" on cows to reduce methane emissions are NOT going to have any effect on what's happening to our climate.

It's only going to force 8 billion people to struggle for survival daily and their constant need to find food, shelter, and security for the people they love (which is already starting to happen) will only force them into a perpetual "crisis mode" and NO ONE will be able to focus enough of their attention to try to affect a change of outcome.

If the People who are creating these issues and then trying to use them to effect change don't realize that "THEY WILL NOT SURVIVE EITHER" and "END THEIR ASSAULT" then everyone on the planet will need to:

- Fasten their safety belts
- Return their tray tables to an upright and locked position
- Assume a "crash position" with your head between your knees,
- Then close your eyes and Pray:
 "that it will be over quickly for the ones you love and care about"

Because we are ALL about to experience turbulence the likes of which is difficult to describe.

5. Yes, "the needs of the many outweigh the needs as a few" is a valid and true concept.

However it can ONLY BE "a very personal belief"

- The concept of sacrificing yourself for the greater good is a personal belief meant for individuals only and only you can decide to act on that belief

It would be intensely immoral for someone to:

- ask you (or try to convince you) to sacrifice yourself

- insist that you sacrifice yourself
- take your life without your consent
- and likewise for you to ask someone to assist who does not also hold that belief

For someone to label others as expendable and plan their deaths means that they have lost the ability to experience compassion or to see the value inherent in all life.

In truth, it is because they have lost their humanity that “their lives will in fact no longer be of any value in the utopian society they are trying to create”

6. Terraforming the planet Mars to make it habitable would be possible with the technology we have today.

Mars is within the goldilocks zone in our solar system and the dwarf planet Ceres in orbit just beyond Mars is made up of Salt Water (an electrolyte).

Introducing the two would:

- wrap the surface of Mars in an electrolyte
- providing a conductive pathway for its telluric current
- which would reestablish its magnetic shield
 - resulting in its ability to support an atmosphere
- and would induce the electromotive force needed for it to begin to spin
- creating a regular daytime and nighttime also

Suggested Reading

- *New perspectives in the study of the Earth’s magnetic field and climate connection: The use of transfer entropy* (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC6237378/>)
- *Geomagnetic South Atlantic Anomaly and global sea level rise: A direct connection?* (<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S1364682611002896>)
- *Glowing Gases - Aurorae: A Spectacular Natural Phenomenon*

[\(https://atoptics.co.uk/blog/glowing-gases-aurorae/\)](https://atoptics.co.uk/blog/glowing-gases-aurorae/)